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Editorial of OSM Science 2024

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In August of this year, 2024, OpenStreetMap (OSM) celebrated its 20th birthday. OSM has grown from a small UK-based mapping project into the largest crowdsourced and volunteered geospatial database in the world. Here, as part of the seventh edition of the Academic Track at the annual State of the Map (SotM) conference, we celebrate the first global SotM on the continent of Africa. This year's OSM Science, as is the case with all previous editions of the Academic Track, delivers a consolidated knowledge hub for the gathering, sharing, and reporting of scientific progress in OSM-related research. Crucially, this platform facilitates the sharing of scientific findings about OSM directly with the broader OSM community. SotM 2024 takes place from the 6th to 8th September 2024 in Nairobi, Kenya with OSM Science and the Academic Track taking place on Sunday September 8th in its own dedicated session. There are 11 short papers corresponding to 7 full talks and 2 lightning talks presented at the conference with an additional 2 lightning talks presented as video talks. In this Editorial, we summarize these papers by briefly discussing their contributions and attempting to group these works into broad but also interrelated research topics. While this grouping reflects our own interpretation of the contributions and research outcomes of each paper, each extended abstract within the proceedings provides more details and information about the corresponding research. We encourage you to look at these works.

Zanchetta et al. [1] consider the challenge of assessing the performance of AI-assisted mapping of building footprints for OSM. Arising from the recent use of AI for mapping assistance in OSM, this work introduces fAIr ("Free and open source AI for Responsible mapping"): a fully open AI-assisted mapping service to generate semi-automated building footprints features developed by the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT). fAIr displays novelty in reintroducing the "human in the loop" for AI-assisted mapping. Currently, as reported by the authors, fAIr allows OSM mappers to create their own local training dataset, train/fine-tune a pre-trained Eff-UNet model, and then map directly within OSM with the assistance of their own local model. fAIr's performance is analyzed using twenty five urban regions and seeks to represent different grades of urban characteristics from different regions of the world. Within the domain of assessing the performance of various mapping approaches, Wang and Zipf [2] present their work on assessing the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of road data in OpenStreetMap.

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This work extends the substantial body of existing research work on OSM data quality by exploring quality dimensions specific to the case of motorized vehicle traffic. It does so by analyzing the attribute accuracy, i.e. whether tag values are available and correct, and logical consistency, i.e. topological correctness, of roads while taking into consideration country-specific laws and regulations. The framework is applied for Germany, relating mostly to speed limit data (in the context of attribute accuracy). Cohen and Nelson [3] also consider the transportation domain with their work on a methodological framework which combines OSMnx and a multilane detection algorithm to produce a Simplified OSM Data (SOD) network. The goal of this simplification process is to use the OSM data for improved active transportation analysis. The simplification relates to the combination of multiple transportation lanes related to active transportation (AT) into single centerlines, thus promoting the computation of various measures that relate to self-propelled human-powered travel modes, e.g. walking and cycling. Ways, in OSM, which share the same name, that show similarity in terms of orientation, and that are in close proximity to each other, are identified as multilane features. The approach is applied to several cities across the world, displaying varying levels of success.

Chukwu et al. [4] investigate the use of OSM data for disaster preparedness in Harare, Zimbabwe. Geospatial data about man-made structures and gasoline stations were added to OSM (where they were missing) and this data was then used to perform risk assessment analyses leading to the identification of danger zones and highly vulnerable areas, especially to fire hazards. Connected to disaster preparedness, Thomas [5] reflects on the outcomes and learning experiences of a Mini-Mapathon project, which involved 28 students within three Human Geography courses at an international high school in Beijing, China. Students were taught the basics of humanitarian mapping and then involved in real-world mapping projects using the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team's (HOT) Tasking Manager. A survey allowed the author to assess students' learnings as well as their motivation and future expectations to remain engaged in mapping projects. We also acknowledge the need to prepare for future climate scenarios and improve sustainability in our interactions with the environment. With this in mind, Lo Presti and Mooney [6] report on an analysis of renewable energy infrastructure representations in OpenStreetMap. To support the renewable energy transition there is a constant need for availability of reliable data about renewable energy infrastructure. In this work, the authors argue that OSM can meet these demands but it is necessary to identify common mapping errors and tagging issues associated with wind and solar energy infrastructures representation within OSM to ensure data quality. The work also presents the results of a geographical analysis to consider the distribution of infrastructures across various land cover types, seeking to detect patterns around land cover and renewable energy infrastructures. Ireland and Belgium are considered in the analysis but extension to more regions and areas is planned in the future. A further example of the use of OSM in the research process is proposed by Strus et al. [7], who involved a group of university students in adding data to OSM through a mix of sources: field mapping using mobile apps, high-resolution imagery, external sources such as scientific publications and a GPS receiver. In addition to providing students with the necessary knowledge to become experienced OSM contributors, the maps generated in this way are then used as a basis for multiple studies in the hydrogeological and urban planning domains.

Tockner et al. [8] consider the changing trends in the global evolution of corporate mapping in OSM. In this work, the authors provide an analysis from continuously monitoring

the impact of large corporate contributors to OSM in regards to their changing patterns of contributions. This is very important towards supporting a stronger, data-driven, understanding of the sustainability of OSM in the longer term. Following on from existing research, this work presents analysis to quantify the impact of corporate editing, particularly on volunteer mapping behavior, as an important measure of the structure and robustness of the OSM community. Along the same theme, Hoferek et al. [9] investigates corporate editors in OSM by considering the demographic makeup, careers, motivations and community relationships of the OSM contributors belonging to corporate editors. Results of a survey indicated multiple groups of corporate editors. Although interesting results on the corporate editors' profiles may be extracted the authors concede that a higher rate of participation from corporate editors in these types of surveys is required to ensure better overall representation. The role of humanitarian projects is often considered in the same conversations as those of corporate editors. In this vein, Rossi [10] describes research on examining how crowd-mapping and PGIS (Participatory GIS) could turn out to be a crucial tool in contributing to humanitarian projects, such as HOTOSM, by playing a role in shaping participatory processes. Fieldwork, reported as part of the research, includes an emergency intervention led by a five NGOs consortium project. The team participated in the HOTOSM Project by mapping different polygons/buildings delimiting territorial areas hit by the earthquake, as a part of an initiative by the Open Mapping Hub for West and Northern Africa. The final paper in our proceedings by Grinberger and Minghini [11] reflects on a systems perspective analysis of the events behind the introduction of rate limiting in OSM. This work uses a specific case in OSM's history – a set of politically-motivated edits deleting and distorting OSM data in Israel – to discuss the vulnerabilities and resilience-enhancing capabilities of the project. By tracing how the reactions to these events had led to the formation of a temporary coalition between the local mapping community and the data working group that was eventually used to mobilize support for a project-wide change - the introduction of a daily rate limit – it shows that the basic assumptions of OSM simultaneously increases the project's vulnerability and promotes resilience.

Overall, our proceedings reflect a wide range of topics, from AI tool application and data quality to sustainability, education, and humanitarian applications. As with SotM conferences of the past, this year's conference continues to demonstrate the diverse and impactful research being conducted within the OSM community. It is thus with great excitement that we look to the future of research with and about OSM, hoping that this OSM Science 2024 meeting will continue to provide contributions to shape and explore the field of scientific exploration of OSM and its long-term research agenda.

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Crisis Mapping: Teaching High School ELL Students How To Make Maps That Save Lives

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This conference paper presents the learning experiences and outcomes of a Mini-Mapathon course developed, implemented, and evaluated for the first time in a population of 28 Asian Junior high school English Language Learner (ELL) students in three Human Geography courses at an international high school in Beijing, China. The paper includes an introduction to crisis mapping, an educational website built by the teacher, and a description of the project-based learning Mini-Mapathons. Prior to the high school crisis mapping courses, three Mini-Mapathons were piloted for 75 Asian 4th grade students in three classrooms after they had learned about crises in their IB-PYP curriculum. Kilometers of roads and number of buildings mapped were measured collectively and shared with participants after each Mini-Mapathon. The paper concludes with an analysis of students' knowledge and skill gains, and attitudes towards map making. Other variables measured included students' interest and motivation for participating in future Mapathons or starting YouthMappers chapters in their future colleges or universities. Students' survey responses were analyzed using mixed methods. A recommendation for further research is proposed.

Never has crisis mapping been more relevant, as disasters are increasing in frequency and severity, resulting in billions of dollars in economic loss and a record-breaking number of people being affected [1, 2]. Crisis mapping is defined as "the real-time gathering, visualizing, and analysis of data during conflict and disaster settings" [3]. In response to disasters, a new form of humanitarianism has emerged: digital humanitarianism in the form of crisis mapping [4]. Crisis mapping is an interactive participatory approach revolutionizing the way crises are understood, reported, and managed. A Mini-Mapathon, a 45-60 minute version of a typical three hour Mapathon, is one way to co-create maps so that vulnerable populations, governments, and NGO's can respond to crises as well as increase awareness and preparedness to reduce risks when disaster strikes. The Mini-Mapathon project objectives were three-fold. First, to teach students how to save lives through maps. Second, to provide students a real world educational and volunteering experience that meets their service-learning requirements. Third, to enhance students' Human Geography knowledge and skills. Using the ADDIE (Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, Evaluate) approach, a Mini-Mapathon curriculum was designed and implemented to answer three research questions below [5].

1. How did the design of Mini-Mapathons support changes in students' perceptions of their crisis mapping knowledge and skills?

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2. How did the participation in the Mini-Mapathon support students' expression of interest in crisis mapping in the future?

3. How did the Mini-Mapathon support students in engaging crisis mapping?

Twenty-eight Asian high school students participated in the Mini-Mapathon so that medicine and services could be delivered to vulnerable populations in Nigeria and Zimbabwe by *Doctors Without Borders* and *The Red Cross*. The Mini-Mapathons for ELL elementary students and ELL high school students were inspired by the Mini-Mapathons launched effectively with 10 year old students in Milan, Italy [6]. After www.hotosm.org accounts were created and students embarked on a virtual field trip to meet the vulnerable population in their geographic area via 2-3 minute YouTube videos from *UNHCR*, *Red Cross*, or *Doctors Without Borders*, step by step in class instructions were implemented to make learning visible and meet the academic language needs of the ELL students [7,8]. During the 45-minute Mini-Mapathons, students were taught how to map buildings and roads using software on www.hotosm.org. Pre and post surveys were collected so that researchers could better understand and measure how students learned during Mini-Mapathons and determine if this innovative methodology for teaching crisis mapping was effective [5].

Figure 1. Photos from the Mini-Mapathon with ELL students for Chad, Africa

In response to *RQ 1 How did the design support changes in students' perceptions of increasing their crisis mapping knowledge and skills?* findings indicated that ELL students effectively increased their geospatial knowledge and skills following their experiential learning of map-making because they were able to follow instructions and construct a crisis map [9]. The process of students learning was through the concrete, transformational experience of creating a map that could be used in the real world [9]. Students' self-assessment of their skills also indicated improvement after the Mini-Mapathon intervention with *Pre Survey Q.3. How would you rate digital map making skills?* mean value 2.92 compared to a mean value of 3.27 in *Post Survey Q.5. How would you rate your digital map making skills?* Many students reported they learned that maps could be collaboratively created by many people and international relief organizations need our help showcasing the tenets of *Connectivism Theory* at work [10]. Finally, through this innovative learning experience, participants were able to gain service-learning hours to meet their requirement to graduate high school through this project-based learning (PBL) Mini-Mapathon.

In response to *Post Survey Q.3 What didn't you know before?*, when given multiple choice along with an open ended answer, 43% of the students indicated they didn't know that maps can be made by many people, 32% learned that maps can be created, and 21% learned

that humanitarian organizations need our help making maps that can be used by their organization. 4% indicated they didn't know mapping is never finished work.

In response to *RQ 2 How did participating in the Mini-Mapathon support student expressed interest in crisis mapping in the future?* Most students indicated they would like to participate in crisis mapping again in the future. Based on survey results of Post Survey Q.7 *What is the likelihood that you would participate in another Mapathon in the future?*, 50% of students said they would be interested in participating in a Mapathon again in high school or university which suggests a positive trend in students' map making experience. Students were also asked if they wanted to lead a crisis mapping chapter in the future. Based on survey results of Post Survey Q.8. *What is the likelihood that you would participate or start a Youth Mappers club at your college or university in the future* two-fifths (43%) stated they would likely or very likely participate in or start a *Youth Mappers* club at their college or university in the future.

In response to RQ 3 How did the Mini-Mapathon support students in engaging crisis mapping? findings indicated that 54% of students indicated that this was the first time constructing a map according to survey results of *Pre Survey Q.6 Have you ever created a map before?* From a constructionist perspective, given that this was fifteen students' first experience map making, we can say that this hands-on, computer-based student learning experience was engaging enough for them to learn because they co-created a tangible product or map [11]. Evidence for learning was that students demonstrated their knowledge to create the map and the number of buildings and kilometers of roads mapped collectively were counted at the end of each class [9].

Student learning through this applied research project follows the literature describing students' positive learning outcomes from a responsive curriculum on disasters [12]. The Mini-Mapathon provided an academic opportunity to critically reflect on current, relevant, and timely disasters affecting vulnerable populations and learn from others' experiences through videos, maps, and text from project descriptions [13]. In this way it met many of the "Optimal Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) Curriculum Practices" including but not limited to, students being given opportunities to assume a catalytic role within local community disaster risk reduction and students being given opportunities to practice disaster risk reduction skills in real life context through action learning [14].

There were several limitations and constraints that impacted sample size and how this project was implemented. First, time was a major limiting factor which led to the shrinking of a 3 hour Mapathon into three 45 minute Mini-Mapathons held in each of the Human Geography classes. Language was also a constraint as some ELL students had very high English language proficiency while others had low English level proficiency. Some students were unable to use the <https://tasks.hotosm.org> mapping software on certain browsers on their tablet devices. Finally, many students were absent due to COVID-19, which resulted in a smaller sample size. Given these similar constraints and limitations in the future, two recommendations for Mini-Mapathons for ELL students would be to move the mapping event into the school's library with 30 desktop Macs and ensure users were already logged into <https://tasks.hotosm.org> using anonymous student ID's in order to save time and reduce IT-related issues with students' tablet devices. Another culturally sensitive recommendation would be to implement Mini-Mapathons in the fall semester in Chinese high schools, as there are often more absences in the spring semester for junior high school students who are granted leave to focus on college applications.

In closing, crisis mapping teaches students that they can change the world one map at a time. Through this innovative, experiential learning activity which many students called “outstanding”, students learned that they can meet service-learning requirements in high school or university through crisis mapping [9]. Crisis mapping can also provide students access to scholarships, internships, and leadership opportunities to create or join a *Maptivist* chapter in high school or *YouthMappers* chapter in their future university. Findings from this Mini-Mapathon project suggested that despite English being a second language for the students, the curriculum and instructions in English were intuitive and engaging enough for students to construct the maps in context, even for first-time mappers [11]. Overall, through participating in this crisis mapping activity students demonstrated improved mapping skills, increased geospatial knowledge, and many indicated they would be interested in participating in crisis mapping events in the future. An innovative instructional website was created, www.crisismapping.weebly.com to supplement <https://teachosm.org> materials for teachers to use as an instructional resource when hosting their very own Mini-Mapathon or to provide crisis mapping instruction to their grade 4-university students to use in formal and informal learning environments around the world.

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The role of crowd-mapping and PGIS in post-emergency humanitarian operations

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Considering that the so-called “digital humanitarianism” can support climate justice by providing tools and platforms for data collection, analysis, and dissemination that empower vulnerable communities to advocate for their rights and mobilize for climate action and advance equitable solutions, we could subscribe it can amplify the voices of marginalized communities, enhance transparency and accountability, and promote greater inclusivity in the fight for climate justice. Authors in [1] state the general opinion that among practitioners, researchers, and activists, the practice of Web-GIS with OSM is more advanced than the underlying theory of its applications. Digital humanitarianism is located at the intersection of new socio-technical practices, a new epistemology, and new institutional relationships [2,3].

Overall, within the context of digital humanitarianism, as demonstrated by web-map services and communities like Ushahidi or the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT), traditional humanitarian organizations delegate tasks connected to the collection, production, processing, dissemination, and mapping of humanitarian data to a vast, participatory network of non-specialist volunteers.

People, giving examples of the huge scale of Volunteer Geographic Information (VGI), contribute to OpenStreetMap [4] and publish their maps, which has proven particularly beneficial in remote regions that Google has not yet covered and which experienced catastrophic events related to natural disasters.

When PGIS (Participatory GIS) maps reflect perceptions of the world (or parts of it), the “qualitative” aspect of GIS is enriched by data gathered through methods like ethnographic interviews, focus groups, and participatory observations [5].

The study aims to precisely examine how crowd-mapping and PGIS could turn out to be a crucial tool in contributing to humanitarian projects by analyzing the specific characteristics and outcomes of the selected application case, identifying the mechanisms through which geospatial data - documented through observations and crowd-sourced data - play a role in shaping participatory processes [6]. By integrating geodata collected and validated by community members into the planning framework, it could be further explored, within the broader research in which this study is integrated, how this participatory approach enhances the accuracy of data, reflects local knowledge, and empowers communities in decision-making. The study fosters collaboration between stakeholders by ensuring that

participatory planning outcomes are more inclusive and responsive to local needs, the criticalities and problems that emerged, and the possible strategies to be activated to tackle them especially in contexts where people living in rural and remote areas and in peri-urban areas face problems such as inadequate access to essential resources, and are more exposed to low quality basic services (health and education) and the effects of natural disasters.

The current case study of planning a humanitarian mapping intervention in a post-emergency context (Morocco 2023) is part of a PhD research project at the University of Palermo's CSTE, with the scientific expertise in Social Lab of researchers from the University of Catania's DISFOR (Department of Educational Sciences) in Italy. The fieldwork is part of an emergency intervention led by a five NGOs consortium project financed by Caritas, where the humanitarian mapping activities were coordinated by COPEOfficinaSociale (Social Research Center of the NGO CO.P.E. Cooperazione Paesi Emergenti) with an overall objective of assisting the population impacted by the earthquake that struck in Morocco on September 8 and 9, 2023. As part of this intervention, which calls for various support measures (distribution of family kits, distribution of housing tents and school modules, social-health interventions and psychological support), a humanitarian mapping action, indeed, has been carried out in collaboration with El Amane Association of Marrakech and the young women of a social radio station called "Radio El Amane" attentive to 'open data'. The project starts from an integrated strategy that brings together humanitarian mapping and "future labs", presenting a dynamic approach to addressing social challenges in post-emergency contexts and crisis areas.

The project was implemented based on 3 strategic milestones: Share of experiences and knowledge on mapping activities and their application in the humanitarian context of reference (phases 1 and 2); geo-data elaboration for disaster risk reduction and response (phases 2 and 3); contribute to the OSM community and develop a project outcome using a story-map tool (phase 3), still in progress.

The project's phases include six components:

1. HOT project (Phase 1) - the team actively participated in the HOT project by mapping different polygons/buildings delimiting territorial areas hit by the earthquake, as a part of an initiative by the Open Mapping Hub for West and Northern Africa. It has engaged a diverse group of contributors across five distinct initiatives, resulting in the collection of a significant amount of data: it shows significant progress toward project completion with 62,535 changesets created by 10,235 contributors (data last consulted June 2024).

2. Mapathon (Phase 2) - the mapping group, consisting of four women (Chaimaa Aaglli, Manar Abissate, Aya Elhourri, Nadia Elmejjati, and the Mapping Coordinator Halima Oulami, President of El Amane Association and researcher at LERMA) and one man (Miloud Ouchala, Professor from University of Marrakech, LERMA), actively participated with three representatives in the mapathon activity held in January 2023. The Emerging Business Factory (EBF) and the Global Diversity Foundation (GDF) worked together to monitor and assess humanitarian efforts following earthquakes in the High Atlas region through the Mapathons website, which uses the Tasking Manager. The mapathon aimed to consolidate data and information on earthquake response via the Mapathons website, utilising established methodologies and prior expertise. Local, national, and international organizations were invited to support EBF's initiative to create an accessible and secure platform for earthquake response activities, providing data, information, and maps.

3. PGIS / Field visits - With concern to the field visit missions in the province of El Haouz and Chichaoua the established mapping team used the following tools and methods: Google Earth Pro for printing maps and involving local residents in their distribution / OsmAnd and Mapillary (Android for digital recording on smartphone devices) / Google Earth Pro and ArcMap for comprehensive mapping / Web-GIS platforms like OSM or Missing Maps, HOT Tasking Manager for data collection / Google Earth Pro, for printing for the focus groups with the community.

The integration with ArcMap was a key methodology adopted to improve location accuracy in OsmAnd. The primary aim of this integration was to overlay the mapped data obtained with their surveys onto existing digital maps. The process began with scanning the printed maps from Google Earth Pro. The mapping team then used ArcMap to merge these scanned maps with the digital maps available in the software. This step allowed them to achieve an integrated representation of the mapped information. Once merged, they integrated the field data into Excel spreadsheets. This allowed them to organize and manipulate the data more effectively, preparing it for seamless integration with digital maps. Subsequently, they converted the data from ArcMap's SHP format to OsmAnd's GPX format. This conversion was crucial to ensure a smooth and uninterrupted data transition between the two systems, enabling seamless integration. Finally, to ensure precise geolocation of points of interest in the douars, considering both territorial landmarks and WEF (Water, Energy, Food) factors, mappers used OsmAnd to automatically geolocate entities based on converted data. This included 1) territorial features such as water sources, wells, and earthquake-damaged roads, and 2) anthropic features like places of worship, schools, small shops, solar energy installations, crops, cooperatives, and interests in forming associations. This approach provided additional assurance of the precision and reliability of the mapped information. The humanitarian mapping process was conducted using participatory methodologies, actively involving local communities in the data collection and analysis. This inclusive approach ensured the representativeness of the collected information and fostered greater engagement from the directly affected individuals. The data collected in the initial mapped douars have been presented in a shared geoportal elaborated with ArcGIS (<https://www.arcgis.com/apps/instant/portfolio/index.html?appid=ddf0601c4eb84adba9dde6a78ac6d6fc>).

4. Future Lab (Phase 2) - On March 24, under the coordination of Professor Augusto Gamuzza from University of Catania (DISFOR), five "future labs", a collaborative initiative designed to address and innovate solutions for challenges, were held in five different douars within the Commune of Assif El Mal (Imi Oussif, Ait Abaid, Tabonout, Tafroukht, Tloutimte). The future labs' working groups were composed of territorial representatives and stakeholders from diverse sectors like volunteers, community leaders, and local organization members (e.g., muqaddim, kaid, school teachers, association representatives). Furthermore, the groups were organized by gender to address specific gender-related needs effectively.

5. OpenStreetMap (Phase 3) - The next step will be to upload the data to OpenStreetMap, which will allow the collected information to be shared with the community and made accessible to a wider audience.

6. Story Map (Phase 3) - The final step will develop a project outcome using a story-map tool, partially developed by the Geo-portal already realized.

This activity provided a thorough understanding of the needs and challenges faced by earthquake-affected communities, using data to guide effective assistance and

reconstruction efforts. For the first time in Morocco's remote areas, the mapping of settlements, land use, and disaster risk zones was accomplished with local knowledge. Various tools and methods were employed for spatial learning and advocacy, including satellite imagery, GPS surveys, participatory mapping, OSM data and HOT initiatives, GIS analysis, complemented by interviews and field surveys (future labs). The integration of Indigenous Geographic Knowledge (IGK) supports peer-to-peer engagement and could turn out to be an important source of information for authorities and policy planners about community concerns. The case study highlights the importance of including diverse geographical perspectives, particularly from women. In the context of Africa, the digital divide is particularly pronounced, with significant progress in digital mapping and other technological advancements being made in industrialized countries, while the field remains largely underexplored in remote areas of the African continent. The fact that the case study was developed in a vulnerable context of North Africa is meant to emphasize the need to address this imbalance.

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Analyzing the Spatial Distribution of Fuel Stations in Harare, Zimbabwe: Leveraging OpenStreetMap for Disaster Preparedness, Mitigation and Recovery

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Natural or man-made disasters pose serious risks to communities all over the world and frequently have dire repercussions, including the loss of life, destruction of property, and disruption of social order [1]. Fire occurrences are particularly dangerous among these calamities, especially when they include infrastructure such as gasoline stations [2]. The potential for large-scale fire catastrophes underscores the need to ensure the safety of gasoline station infrastructure, as evidenced by occurrences documented in Zimbabwe [3]. Petroleum derivatives, such as gasoline, diesel, kerosene, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), have the potential to ignite fires when handled improperly [4]. It is clear that a comprehensive fire danger assessment is necessary, which highlights the need for proactive fire management planning [4]. Between 1993 and 2004, there were around 243 fire-related incidents at fuel service stations worldwide that were recorded [5]. It is evident that these sites present significant risks.

Geospatial technology has become an invaluable instrument for disaster preparedness, response, and mitigation as a result of these issues [6]. By offering open data necessary for disaster response and mitigation, initiatives such as the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) and the utilization of platforms similar to OpenStreetMap (OSM) have made substantial progress in these efforts [7]. These systems ensure the availability of high-quality data for efficient mitigation measures and provide quick and open access to geospatial data, facilitating prompt disaster response activities [8]. The OSM data consists of many datasets that use points, lines, polygons, and area attributes to represent real-world features [9,10]. These databases include characteristics that are useful for study, mitigation, recovery, and preparedness for disasters.

Through querying the OSM database using the QuickOSM plugin [11] on the Quantum Geographic Information System (QGIS) [12], there were only 54 petrol stations in Harare

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listed in the OSM database. After identifying this gap, petrol station addresses were collected from the Zimbabwe Petroleum Regulatory Authority (ZPRA). This revealed that there are actually 324 petrol stations in Harare, meaning 288 petrol stations are missing from the OSM database. Using GIS techniques and the Java OpenStreetMap Editor (JOSM) [13] and EveryDoor [14] open-source mobile application, the remaining 288 petrol stations were mapped into the OSM database.

This research aimed to address the challenges posed by fire hazards, particularly in petrol station infrastructure, through the application of GIS techniques. The study conducted geoprocessing analyses, including overlay and proximity analysis, using building footprints, conventional construction standards for the siting of petroleum liquid and gas facilities, and public spaces such as markets, parks, schools, hospitals, places of worship, and road networks in Harare, Zimbabwe. Also, nearest neighbor analysis and Euclidean distance analysis [15] were performed using petrol station points to identify danger zones and potential vulnerabilities. The study also sought to map petrol stations, obtain their exact locations, and extract pertinent data from OSM and other sources using GIS methodologies. The study also aims to categorize areas at risk of fire hazards based on various factors, such as proximity to fuel stations and the location of filling stations according to Zimbabwean government regulations and retail premises, as well as other factors identified through spatial analysis.

Furthermore, it sought to offer practical suggestions and solutions for improving public safety and lessening the effects of fire disasters in Harare, Zimbabwe, offering insightful information for initiatives related to disaster preparation, mitigation, and recovery to advance resilience and sustainable development in the country while also adding to the scientific understanding of the dangers of fire hazards related to gasoline stations as well as providing a replicable approach to mapping external data into the OSM database.

This study's methodology combines spatial analytic methodologies and data extraction from GIS analysis. To fully comprehend the gaps that now exist, the research first starts by gaining access to the data that is already available on the OSM Database. The gasoline stations missing in the OSM database were then mapped into the database, where pertinent data such as locations and infrastructure aspects were recorded. Then relevant data was extracted from OSM. The procedure involved extracting comprehensive information on the locations of buildings, roads, and public spaces, including playgrounds, marketplaces, hospitals, and schools, from the massive OSM database. This extraction was done using the QuickOSM plugin on QGIS software, which shows the richness of the OSM database and the procedures used in this study are provided and detailed in the methodology section. All geospatial datasets, including those from OSM and the Zimbabwe Petroleum Regulatory Authority (ZPRA), are attached and accessible for replication of the analysis.

A thorough examination of the geographic distribution of filling stations, public buildings, and fire service stations was done using the GIS technique. The objective of this research was to categorize areas at risk of fire hazards according to the Zimbabwean government's standards for the placement of retail and LPG filling stations. These rules include factors such as the distance from fuel stations and other infrastructural concerns. To fully comprehend the spatial distribution of fuel stations in relation to fire stations, residential buildings, and public amenities like schools, hospitals, places of worship, markets, parks, and more, techniques like Euclidean, nearest neighborhood analysis, and

geoprocessing analysis were used. The mapping results are presented as maps, graphs and tables, where the identified risk zones are visualized, and detailed analysis is provided.

To perform the analysis, the number of buildings in each of the four fire danger risk zones—very high, high, medium, and low risk—was grouped and examined. In order to determine the number of structures in each of these designated zones, a query to the OSM dataset was made. This yields important information on the possible effects of fire hazard events on different regions within the research area.

This study aimed to provide crucial information for risk and disaster management (preparedness, mitigation, and recovery) by conducting a thorough investigation of fire hazard threats associated with petrol stations in Harare, Zimbabwe. Utilizing GIS techniques and geospatial data from OSM, the project sought to improve public safety, mitigate the effects of fire disasters, and advance the scientific understanding of fire hazard risks. The methodology, which included collaboration with government agencies, ensured that essential data, such as petrol station addresses and coordinates provided by the Zimbabwe Petroleum Regulatory Authority (ZPRA), were accurately uploaded and integrated into the OSM database. This was achieved using the JOSM, with validation through the EveryDoor mobile application, ensuring data alignment with OSM's structure and protocols.

The study identified significant data gaps within OSM, particularly the absence of many petrol stations in Harare, which were addressed by integrating the ZPRA datasets. While OSM proved to be a valuable source of geospatial data, the study highlights the need for continuous updates and systematic data validation to enhance its utility. Recommendations include encouraging policymakers to leverage OSM for disaster risk reduction strategies and fostering collaborations between government agencies and the OSM community to ensure data accuracy and relevance.

The findings and recommendations of this study emphasize the importance of integrating external datasets with open-source geospatial databases to improve hazard mapping and risk management efforts. By doing so, it is possible to enhance public safety and disaster preparedness, making OSM a more reliable tool for both local and global disaster response initiatives.

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Assessing the performance of AI-assisted mapping of building footprints for OSM

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Building footprints features are useful in a wide range of applications such as disaster assessment, urban planning, and environmental monitoring [1-3], and their identification has been gaining increasing interest and attention from the machine learning (ML) research in Earth Observation [4]. In the context of disaster response, accurate and prompt availability of such information is crucial [5-7]. Open source datasets of AI-generated building footprints exist (e.g. Microsoft's global buildings dataset, available through Rapid, and Google's Open Buildings for Africa and the Global South at large); however, the ML models underlying these datasets are not currently open sourced [8].

fAIr, a fully open AI-assisted mapping service to generate semi-automated building footprints features developed by the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) [9], addresses this need. fAIr stands for "Free and open source AI for Responsible mapping, that is resilient to local contexts and relates to local communities", reflecting the objective of HOT to improve and assist mapping for humanitarian aid and disaster relief. In particular, fAIr performs semantic segmentation to detect building footprints from imagery at high resolution (cm) openly available through OpenAerialMap (OAM) [10]. OAM is an open service that provides search and access to openly licensed satellite and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) imagery uploaded by users to its website.

While in OSM building footprints mapping is currently supported in most countries through Rapid, the need remains for adjustments and corrections [11]. fAIr addresses this issue by reintroducing the *human in the loop*. In its current state, fAIr allows OSM mappers to create their own local training dataset, train/fine-tune a pre-trained Eff-UNet model, and then map into OSM with the assistance of their own local model.

In its initial release [8], the performance of the model following training was not assessed; the objective of this research is to address this gap. This paper describes the research developed to assess how the ML fine-tuning process performs, investigating the currently used accuracy metric, and comparing against different sets of evaluation metrics. This falls within the broader spectrum of research on understanding the fine-tuning process for geographic domain adaptation in image analysis validation [12,13]. The ultimate aim of this research is to advise on the performance of fAIr, by assessing the current validation accuracy and comparing against other accuracy metrics for building footprints segmentation tasks.

To test fAIr's performance, we selected twenty five urban regions from OAM imagery, seeking to represent different grades of urban characteristics from different regions of the world. The urban regions were categorised by three variables through visual inspection: *urbanity*, meaning the degree of urbanity per each region, with classes: 'rural', 'peri-urban', 'urban', 'refugee camp'; *urban density*, with classes: 'sparse', 'dense', 'grid' (a class in between sparse and dense, which shows a regular gridded or repeated spatial pattern); *roof cover type*, with classes: 'shingles', 'metal' (usually tin), 'cement', 'mixed' (a mix of the above, or other types). We then performed manual labelling on selected areas of interest (Aoi), leveraging OSM data when this was available and aligned, or else generating new OSM data while labelling the images (see fAIr-dev website [14] for a detailed explanation on the labelling process). The pre-processing of the Aoi images, to generate one training dataset per urban region, was performed through fAIr-dev website [14] and produced 256x256 georeferenced tiles for both the original RGB images (ground truth) and OSM data (the labels), where the latest were converted to binary masks for the analysis. The number of tiles per region varies depending on the training dataset, for a total of 8400 images (about 350 per region in average) at three different zoom levels (19, 20, 21).

Having labelled the Aois, the next step was semantic segmentation. In computer vision (CV), semantic segmentation is the task of segmenting an image into semantic meaningful classes, which is performed with convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures [15]. The deep learning CNN model used in fAIr is called RAMP (Replicable AI for MicroPlanning), and its architecture originates from a typical encoder-decoder network, a computational process where images are trained on labelled data, called Eff-UNet model [16]. This consists of an EfficientNet as the encoder for feature extraction, with UNet decoder for reconstructing the segmentation map [17]. RAMP was chosen as an outcome of a series of feasibility studies and AI challenges to segmenting buildings for disaster resilience, happening between 2020 - 2022 and supported by HOT and other international bodies [8].

fAIr is trained using *categorical accuracy* (i.e. the ratio of samples that were correctly classified over all predictions made) at the pixel level as an accuracy metric, with categorical cross entropy as the loss function. Based on a literature review of the performance of metrics in image analysis validation, we chose to compare the current metric against four commonly used validation metrics [13; 18]: *precision*, also known as Positive Predictive Value (PPV), the fraction of actual positive samples among the positive predictions; *recall*, also called sensitivity or True Positive Rate (TPR), the fraction of true positive predictions over all positive samples; *F1 score*, the harmonic mean of PPV and TPR; *intersection over union* (IoU), also known as Jaccard index, a measure of the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth.

We ran the ML training on all twenty five training datasets using an Nvidia Tesla T4 GPU, at four different batch sizes (2, 4, 8 and 16), and for a number of epochs fixed to 20, to be consistent with the current functioning and suggestions of fAIr. For each urban region, the training provided a fine-tuned model backbone, and the value at each epoch of the five metrics, defined using built-in Tensorflow functions. In order to use the fine-tuned model backbones for inference later on, fAIr needs to store the model checkpoints. This is currently done using early-stopping, which means that the model is stored at the epoch at which the categorical accuracy has its maximum value for validation during training. In our analysis we consider this epoch, per each urban region, as the benchmark against which to evaluate the

model performance. In other words, when categorical accuracy is at its highest, how do other metrics perform? In particular, how about IoU, which is the suggested metric for this type of image analysis problem [13]?

In a preliminary analysis we compared the values of each metric against one another, at the epoch at which categorical accuracy was the highest for validation after training. This was done taking into account the three variables mentioned above, and it showed that the degree of urbanity and roof type do not seem to have a relevant influence on the performance, at least for the twenty five regions considered in the analysis, and were therefore discarded. When considering only the density variable, an analysis on the batch size showed that the distribution of the metrics is consistent across the batch sizes, with variations being attributable mainly to density; therefore the batch size is also discarded as a variable.

The values for all the metrics grouped by the density classes are plotted in Figure 1 for the four batch sizes (2, 4, 8 and 16), and for all the urban regions. Clearly a trend is seen going from sparse to dense urban regions, with IoU and recall performances being mostly affected. The results thus point to density being the major driver in affecting the model accuracy during validation. Among all the twenty five selected urban regions and for all the accuracy metrics, dense regions perform worse on average, 4.2% less than sparse and 4.8% less than grid regions. These figures grow respectively to 7.8% and 7.7% when considering IoU alone. While ideally both precision and recall should have high values (closer to 1), in our

Figure 1. Boxplot with values of five validation accuracy metrics (categorical accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, IoU) for each urban region (left y axis) and grouped by the density variable (right y axis), for four batch sizes (2, 4, 8, 16, bottom x axis).

case high values for precision mean that most detected objects match ground truth objects, but low recall implies that many ground truth objects have been missed, and this also affects F1 score. Low values for IoU imply that the model struggles in distinguishing objects from their backgrounds, a behavior that resonates with more densely populated areas in this case.

In conclusion, fAIr shows to have more potential for mapping buildings in sparsely populated areas than in urban centres. When using fAIr at its current state, one should be aware that building footprints segmentation in dense areas will be less performant than in gridded and sparse areas, with IoU, the recommended metric for this CV task, giving the lowest model performance. Other factors, like the roof cover type and regionality, do not seem to have a relevant effect on the model performance. Future research will concentrate on using other factors to help drive the fine-tuning process, like loss regularisation, and on how other variables, like the zoom level, can affect the performance. The analysis will also be extended to the assessment of the inference process. All the code used in the research is available at <https://github.com/ciupava/fAIr-utilities>, while the preprocessed data is downloadable directly from the fAIr-dev website [14].

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Shifting trends in global evolution of corporate mapping in OSM

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In recent years, with the emergence of corporate editing in OpenStreetMap (OSM), there has been interest, and in some cases concern, about its influence in OSM. For instance, large corporations such as Apple, Microsoft, Meta and Amazon have hired large teams to edit in OSM [1]. The launch of the Overture Maps Foundation, by Amazon, Meta, Microsoft and TomTom hosted by the Linux Foundation in 2022 and the release of its first dataset [2] has also led to heated debates on the OSM forum, regarding the future of OSM. Concerns have been raised about the monopolization of geodata, the replacement of OSM by other sites or the backlining of OSM [3]. Consequently, analyzing and continuously monitoring the impact of corporate contributors and continuing to observe their fluctuating patterns of editing will be significant to the understanding of the sustainability of OSM. Therefore, this talk will look at corporate editing in OSM at three scales - global, national and local to answer the two research questions:

- (RQ1) What is the impact of corporate mapping on global scale mapping?
- (RQ2) What is the impact of corporate mapping on country and small-scale mapping?

There are two main avenues to track corporate contributors: Either through corporate affiliated OSM User IDs (UIDs) or through corporate hashtags in OSM changesets. UIDs of corporation affiliated mappers have been used in the past to track corporate activity in OSM (e.g. [1,4,5]). A list of affiliated usernames can be collected from disclosed lists on the OSM Wiki or corporations GitHub pages [6]. The second way to track corporate edits is through corporate hashtags in changesets. Since 2009, it became possible to add hashtags to changesets in OSM, and this has become common practice, especially to show affiliation to regions, events, organizations or corporations [7]. For the analysis presented here, in total 24 companies were tracked including Apple, Kaart, Amazon, Microsoft, TomTom, Grab, DigitalEgypt, Mapbox and Meta. We used tracking with hashtags as proposed by [7]. The dataset used for the analysis integrated data from two sources: The OpenStreetMap History Database [8] and the OSM Changeset database. The OSHDB was used to derive OSM geometries and attribute information as well as information about the editors. The data was then intersected with a dataset of country boundaries to assign a mapping to a specific country. The OSM changeset dataset was joined to this contribution dataset. The dataset included a plethora of information, but the most relevant columns for the analysis were the OSM ID, Changeset timestamp, hashtags and User IDs, country, year and month as well as

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the geometry information – including the centroids. (We aim at presenting this dataset in detail in another workshop at SOTM 2024.)

At the global level, two analyses were carried out. First, the temporal development of corporate and total edits from 2016-01-01 – 2023-12-31, including a breakdown by individual corporation. Second, the absolute number of corporate edits per country and the percentage of corporate edits based on total edits per country for the period 2019-06-01 to 2023-05-31 were analyzed. For an additional overview, the country-level results were grouped by Human Development Index (HDI) class, for a more in depth understanding of the spatial distribution of corporate edits in respect to socio-economic factors.

Countries with more than 15% corporate edits and more than 100,000 total edits in this period were selected for an in-depth analysis. A total of 28 countries met these requirements and we extracted the monthly corporate and non-corporate edits. The overall time frame for analysis was divided into two time periods: t0 (2019-06-01 – 2021-05-31) and t1 (2021-06-01 – 2023-05-31). For each country we derived the change in average activity for both corporate and non-corporate mapping. Three countries were selected from the 28 countries with high corporate mapping activity for the small-scale analysis: Colombia, Indonesia and the United Arab Emirates. The decision was based on the following criteria: 1) corporate involvement existed at a larger scale 2) an active OSM user base was present and 3) corporations were involved in OSM mapping for several years. For these countries we produced a high-resolution spatial dataset based on a H3 grid utilizing the centroid geometry of each OSM contribution. We performed a spatial auto-correlation analysis to identify regions where corporate (and non-corporate) edits have increased / declined over the past years. In addition to the maps, a normalized confusion matrix was calculated to compare the spatial autocorrelation results and present the overlap or difference between the trends in corporate and non-corporate mapping.

Figure 1. The absolute number of corporate edits and the percentage of corporate edits per country for the timeframe 2019-06-01 – 2023-05-31. Figure produced with QGIS version 3.34.

At the global scale (RQ1), corporate editing increased from 2016 to 2021 and has decreased since then. There is a wide variety of companies involved in OSM, but the large number of edits and its concurrent decrease in edits is mainly driven by three companies, namely Meta, Kaart and Apple. Other researchers have investigated corporate mapping activity [1,4,7], but a decline in their mapping activity has not yet been reported or expected. The observed decline is particularly evident in the case of Apple, which experienced a peak in edits during 2020 (14 million edits) and 2021 (12 million edits) before decreasing by more than half in 2022 (4 million edits).

Corporate edits are concentrated in high and medium HDI regions, with almost 80% of edits distributed across 32 countries. As seen in other analyses, non-organised mapping tends to focus on very high HDI regions [9], while humanitarian mapping tends to focus on low HDI regions [10]. The results presented here suggest that corporate mapping tends to focus more on high and medium HDI regions. The discussion about digital inequalities and power imbalances that may arise from corporate contributions in particular countries or regions should be ongoing, as it is a discussion for OSM as a whole. As of now, it is not clear why the large tech corporations map less. At the same time, it is unlikely that all high and medium HDI countries are completely mapped in OSM already [10].

Regarding the small-scale analysis, our results show that there is no strong correlation between the increase or decrease in the mean corporate or non-corporate edits for the three selected countries. For most regions with a strong increase (high-high cluster) or decrease (low-low cluster) in corporate or non-corporate edits, there is no significant change for the other. This suggests that there is only a rather small influence of corporate mapping dynamics on other parts of the OSM mapping community in a country.

The ability to quantify the impact of corporate editing, particularly on volunteer mapping behavior, continues to be an important measure for the OSM community. For example, further investigation would be necessary to understand the intentions and impacts of corporate mapping for various map features (not just looking at overall edit count). Understanding the intentions of different groups and communities in OSM and their impact on the data is a core necessity to obtain 'OSM Data Literacy', especially for everyone who relies on high quality OSM data for research, business or decision making.

The code and data for analysis can be found at [11].

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Analysis of renewable energy infrastructure representations in OpenStreetMap

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Building a more environmentally sustainable future requires continued development of renewable energy infrastructure. Support for the renewable energy transition calls for the availability of reliable data about energy supply, infrastructures, and environmental impact [1]. OpenStreetMap (OSM) can meet these data requirements. In this work, we describe our research on evaluating the OSM database as a source of data for the study of wind and solar energy infrastructures. As a case-study, we consider two European countries, namely Belgium and Ireland but the work is extendible to other countries and regions. Data within OSM is well-known to have a diverse level of completeness and granularity [2]. However, considering OSM's vibrant mapping communities coupled with both (a) the environmental visibility of wind and solar energy infrastructures, and (b) their relatively limited number compared to other built infrastructures, it is reasonable to assume that the majority of these installations are well mapped within OSM. OSM energy-related objects are widely reported under the "power" tag, with available key-value combinations to identify wind and solar sources. Wind turbines are commonly tagged as "power=generator" and "generator:source=wind", while solar farms are identified as "power=plant" and "plant:source=solar". Over the past few years, the OSM community has expanded its mapping efforts for these tags. For instance, the OSM Tag Info page for solar plants shows an increase from under 5,000 instances in 2020 to over 60,000 by mid-2024 globally. Furthermore, the geographical distribution of these tags highlights a significant concentration of mapping activities in Europe compared to other regions. By combining OSM data with the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) inventory, we consider two research questions. Firstly, we seek to identify common mapping errors and tagging issues associated with wind and solar energy infrastructures representation within OSM. This involves examining geometries and tagging mistakes while evaluating the accuracy and completeness of infrastructures data. Secondly, we perform a geographical analysis to consider the distribution of infrastructures across various CLC, seeking to detect patterns around land covers and renewable energy infrastructures.

Our methodology is summarized as follows: OSM data, in PBF format, is downloaded from GeoFabrik. For our initial investigations, we consider Ireland and Belgium due to local knowledge and their manageable data sizes. Analyses are performed using Python and the *osmium* library, and source code is openly available on GitHub in documented Jupyter notebooks [3]. We answer our research questions using three key steps:

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1. Assess available wind and solar infrastructures in OSM for the correctness of OSM data types and potential geometric errors.
2. Differentiate between individual installations and larger “farms”, to evaluate the quality and completeness of OSM data.
3. Investigate commonalities around land use surrounding renewable energy infrastructures using CLC.

At the outset, power-related data is extracted using the custom `PowerSourceHandler` class, developed by inheriting from `osmium SimpleHandler`. This class was designed to examine a PBF file and extract all OSM objects with “power” tag equal to “plant” or “generator”, yielding a full listing of all available power sources. We filter solar and wind sources based on the “generator:source” or “plant:source” tags. The accuracy of the OSM data types and geometries is checked before moving to “farms”.

To accurately differentiate single installations from farms, we analyze solar and wind sources separately due to their different geometric nature. We employ a point-in-polygon search with spatial indexes to assign nodes – of either wind or solar type – to intersecting areas of the same energy type. This process raises some geometric questions concerning the meaning of areas without nodes and with nodes not linked to any area. We observed several mapping and tagging issues: (a) not mapping individual panels within solar farms or defining turbines as circular areas, (b) nodes not associated with any area, (c) unlinked solar nodes representing private installations (rooftop solar panels or solar thermal collectors), (d) the absence of OSM areas or relations for turbines, frequently indicating incomplete mapping. This final issue is significant: currently, 91.4% of wind nodes in Belgium and around 87.4% in Ireland are not located within any mapped area. Considering the limited number of turbines included in OSM areas or relations, we employed spatial clustering on all turbines to identify wind farms and validate our findings by automatically comparing clusters with existing OSM areas and relations. As a density-based spatial clustering, DBSCAN (Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise) is particularly well suited for this purpose. The algorithm requires us to specify the minimum number of samples in a cluster, and the maximum distance between two samples for them to belong to the same neighborhood. The latter is to be considered one of the most important parameters influencing results: considering the characteristics of onshore wind energy infrastructures, we define the maximum average distance for onshore turbines belonging to the same farm as 5 times the rotor diameter [4]. Despite the availability of the OSM tag “rotor:diameter” for reporting the exact value of the rotor diameter, this attribute is often not reported. Thus, we assume a diameter value of 130 meters for all turbines [4]. Comparing clustering results with OSM data allows us to evaluate quality and completeness of areas and relations, to identify new farms, and to extend existing linkages to unassigned infrastructures.

Due to their geometric nature, the same process cannot be applied to solar infrastructures. All remaining solar data are defined as areas, complicating the automated differentiation between individual installations and solar farms. Our methodology consists of two different processes, based on the value of the `power` tag (“generator” or “plant”). Although the OSM wiki guidelines state that solar farms should be tagged as “plant”, deviations from this standard are possible. To address this issue and avoid discarding valid data, we conduct an area-in-area search on solar generators. This approach assumes that if

a solar generator area encompasses multiple solar generators, it may denote a farm. This process enables us to identify a few tagging mistakes where the “generator” value was used instead of “plant”. Manual examination confirms the correctness of our approach. While it may be possible to apply the same approach on solar “plant”, this would cause a significant data loss, thus we opt for keeping all plant-objects. Ultimately, this decision is strongly dependent on the data accuracy requirements.

The refined datasets provide a comprehensive overview of wind and solar energy sources, facilitating further analyses into renewable energy. Relevant environmental considerations lay on the analysis of land uses around these infrastructures. We retrieved this information from the CORINE database, considering an intermediate level of land type detail (CORINE LABEL2). By evaluating land uses within an arbitrary 1000-meter buffer, we may identify consistent patterns as well as countries' peculiarities. In Belgium, around 18% of wind farms are located within 1000 meters from heterogeneous agricultural areas, while 17% and 15% are near urban fabric and arable land respectively. In Ireland, most wind farms are near pastures (~24%), scrub (~18%) and forests (~18%). We noticed how agricultural areas, in the form of heterogeneous agricultural areas, pastures, or arable land seem to prevail in both contexts. Notably, about 15% of Irish wind farms are close to inland wetlands, mainly peat bogs (CORINE LABEL3), which serve as a natural carbon storage. Figure 1 provides an example. In contrast, this proximity is minimal in Belgium (~0.3%). Monitoring infrastructure near these sensitive areas in Ireland is crucial to prevent negative impacts. For wind energy, artificial surfaces appear relevant only in Belgium; however, both countries have solar farms near urban fabric land cover. Within the buffer from solar infrastructures this LC appears ~19% of the time in Belgium and ~12% in Ireland. In Belgium, heterogeneous agricultural areas (~19%) and forests (~12%) are also significant, while pastures predominate in Ireland (~31%), followed by arable land (~16%). However, it is worth noticing that 56% of the Irish territory is classified as pasture LC. If planned well, the installation of solar infrastructures on various types of agricultural land may create agrivoltaic opportunities, with several potential benefits such as improved crop yields and reduced water usage and enhanced soil moisture retention.

This work considered how to assess and improve completeness and accuracy of renewable energy infrastructure data in OSM. Our analysis distinguishes between individual installations and larger farms, enhancing available data with spatial methodologies. Our based on density-based clustering for identifying wind farms allows evaluation of the OSM data. We employ geocomputation methods to associate solar panels to farms, mitigating tagging errors. We highlighted challenges stemming from inconsistent mapping practices, deviating from OSM guidelines for tag usage and geometry types. Despite these issues, the refined datasets offer comprehensive insights into wind and solar energy sources, enabling deeper analyses and assessment of their integration into the surrounding landscape.

Overall, our small study highlights strengths and limitations of OSM data for renewable energy analysis while offering practical tools (shared in Jupyter notebooks) to assess and enhance overall data quality. We find that OSM has great value and potential as a data source for those considering analysis of renewable energy infrastructure deployment, particularly in contexts where official data are lacking or not publicly available. Future work will include validating our approach for a larger set of countries and regions, while integrating further internal and external completeness and quality evaluations. The latter may be facilitated in countries where renewable energy data are openly available, such as

Norway. We did not process the OSM for larger countries but checked the OHSOME dashboard [5] for more insights. According to this dashboard, since July 2021 wind generator mapping in Ireland and Belgium has risen by 36.5% and 14.3% respectively, while solar generator objects have grown by 1154% and 448%. Significant growing trends are present also in other European countries for the same period. Finally, further research is needed to assess the completeness of other infrastructure-related tags, such as operator, installation date, and generator output values.

Figure 1. Example of wind farms near peat bogs in Ireland. Red lines mark 1000-meter buffers around wind farms, with land cover shown according to CLC. The map in the bottom right corner highlights the zoomed area with a blue circle.

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From Complexity to Clarity: Simplifying OpenStreetMap Data for Improved Active Transportation Analysis

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Active Transportation (AT) refers to self-propelled, human-powered travel modes like walking and cycling [1]. To effectively analyze AT in urban environments, the availability of accurate street network data is paramount. Detailed information on street layout, connectivity, and accessibility [2] is crucial for supporting the evaluation and understanding of walking and bicycling patterns. Combining this information with demographic and environmental factors such as population demographics, AT-related crashes, and land use not only informs infrastructure improvements but also guides strategy development [3]. Such strategies aim to enhance the safety, efficiency, and attractiveness of AT [4,5], thereby mitigating issues such as traffic congestion, obesity, and air pollution [6].

Street network data comes from various sources, each presenting challenges regarding accuracy and update frequency. OpenStreetMap (OSM) offers a comprehensive, open-source geospatial database that is continuously updated by a global community of contributors [7]. OSM's strengths lie in its detailed coverage of road networks, including pedestrian pathways and bicycle lanes, which are crucial for AT analysis [8]. However, utilizing OSM data for AT analysis involves several challenges. Firstly, the granularity of its network can complicate modeling AT users' movements at the street level. For instance, when assessing AT safety or developing a walkability index, the current data representativeness on OSM requires significant manipulation to mitigate bias. Furthermore, due to OSM's open-editing model, the standards for mapping elements are not consistently defined, leading to contentions and variations in data quality [9]. Contributors often map elements based on personal needs and knowledge, introducing inconsistencies in the dataset [10,11]. As a result, in some areas, all designated lanes for various users are meticulously mapped, while in others, only a single lane representing the presence of a street is depicted [12,13]. Additionally, there are instances where only lanes for motor vehicles are detailed, with scant attention paid to lanes catering to other user groups. These inconsistencies necessitate careful consideration and significant data processing when using OSM for AT analysis to ensure accuracy and reliability.

In this study, we propose an innovative solution to generate an axial network specifically designed for monitoring and analyzing AT users, using exclusively OSM data

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(<https://github.com/achic19/SOD>). Our approach simplifies the network while preserving its topology. We apply this solution across diverse spatial contexts, from straightforward geographic regions to complex urban environments. Furthermore, we implement our methodology in several cities worldwide – Turin (Italy), Tel Aviv (Israel), and San Francisco (United State) – each characterized by unique urban structures.

The preliminary tasks use OSMnx [4] to acquire OSM street network data, converting it into a graph while correcting topological errors. Then, the data is stored in a geodata table, including polyline geometry, names, and road types. Our algorithm filters out unsuitable roads, like motorways and trunk roads, and replaces roundabouts with their central points.

The network is then ready for the multilane detection algorithm. Polylines identified in a multilane scenario are aggregated into a centerline and added to the Simplified OSM Data (SOD) network. Other polylines are added to the SOD network, retaining their original geometry. A multilane scenario is identified when polylines share the same street name, have similar angles, and are close together. Polylines are grouped by street name, and azimuth (0° - 180°) narrows the angle range to ensure that parallel lines are considered parallel, regardless of orientation. The Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) clusters similarly angled polylines using a 10° radius and a minimum of two samples. Through sensitivity tests, we determined that a 10° threshold effectively includes nearly parallel polylines while excluding those that are significantly misaligned. Outliers with significantly different angles are excluded. The remaining clusters apply a right and left shifted buffer to each polyline. If two or more polylines in the same class overlap by at least 10% in the shifted buffer, they're classified as multilane, and the entire class is replaced with one or more centerlines. The 10% threshold balances sensitivity (detecting true parallel lines) and specificity by minimizing false positives from minor geometric variations, such as slight bends or irregularities.

The core idea behind creating a new centerline is to identify its start and end vertices and then add intermediate vertices to preserve the overall shape of multilane polylines. Overlapping buffers are merged into a single polygon, and the two polygon vertices that best define the original polylines are used to establish the new centerline's start and end. Intermediate vertices are then added at regular intervals to maintain the original polylines' orientation.

The simplification process introduces significant changes to the locations of many polylines, resulting in issues of continuity, topology, accuracy, and inconsistency in the SOD network. Most problems can be resolved using existing methods, but connecting roundabouts requires extra effort. This process has three steps: transforming the roundabout representation to a point, connecting nearby dead-end polylines, and linking polylines in proximity. Following these steps ensures proper continuity and maintains the network's topology.

The case study centered on Turin, Italy, simplified its street network to 10,535 polylines from an initial 55,104. This effort reduced the complexity of 459 streets, converting 155 roundabouts to single points. Despite some challenges near intersections, the final version preserved topology (see Figure 1).

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Figure 1. displays various urban configurations before (represented by the red network) and after (illustrated by the blue network) the simplification process. These configurations range from simpler layouts (Figure 1a to Figure 1c), where streets are represented with a single lane, to intermediate complexity (Figure 1d - Figure 1f) featuring streets with two lanes, and finally, more intricate arrangements (Figure 1g - Figure 1i).

For validation, 46 streets in Turin were reviewed, revealing a 63% success rate, 22% with minor flaws, and 9% with partial success. Issues such as threshold errors, external mapping inaccuracies, and ambiguous street configurations affected the results. Similar challenges were faced in Tel Aviv, Israel, where 82% of 22 test streets matched perfectly with the reference network. Yet, 9% had minor issues, and 5% achieved partial identification/success. In San Francisco, the results showed 85% accuracy with 20 streets evaluated. While most streets were correctly simplified, minor flaws were present in a few cases. Overall, the methodology successfully streamlined street networks, although it achieved varying rates of success across different cities.

Our study offers a robust methodology for generating axial networks for AT users using OSM data, balancing data simplification with topology preservation. Its successful application across diverse cities such as Turin, Tel Aviv, and San Francisco demonstrate its versatility and effectiveness in varied urban environments. The approach simplifies the complex urban network data, streamlining pedestrian and bicycle analysis while retaining essential details. This enables urban planners and policymakers to better monitor and understand AT patterns, leading to infrastructure improvements that support safer, more efficient, and environmentally friendly urban mobility.

Our research offers both scientific contributions and practical benefits. Scientifically, it has been applied to evaluate the built environment for pedestrian walkability using a spatial data clustering approach. Additionally, it has been utilized in research to evaluate safety and bike network connectivity, aiming to improve bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure in California cities. Practically, this work has been published on GitHub, making the code accessible to everyone for their specific needs and goals.

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Beyond the seventh mountain, beyond the seventh river – OpenStreetMap as a base map in geographical research

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The speech is the result of exercises conducted by employees of the Geoinformation Research Team and students of the UKEN University in Krakow, Poland. The basic assumption we made is that OpenStreetMap can be sufficient as a data provider for various geographical works – as a base map for field exercises, as an almost complete environmental database for some compact area (such as an island or a national park). After reviewing the list of tags describing the geographic environment in OpenStreetMap (OSM) [1], we knew this would be possible. We have selected several research polygons, which we call cartographic polygons. These include the Peljesac Peninsula [2,3] in Croatia (see Figure 1), the Aegean Coast near Thessaloniki in Greece, the area around Lake Inari, the Lemenjoki National Park in Finland, and the wild Bieszczady Mountains in Poland. We selected the training fields so that they were either places with nature close to natural conditions and places significantly transformed by human activity. Usually, these were also important places for some key reasons - for example, on the Peljesac Peninsula, a bridge was built to facilitate communication between the two parts of Dalmatia. Not all places were visited, but we have collected cartographic material for all of them. Before each trip, we trained a group of participants on how to use and supplement OSM. Each participant set up their own user account. Field work consisted of completing the content of OSM as accurately as possible - groups of two people were sent into the field and, using the OsmAnd or EveryDoor applications, they inserted all interesting objects on the map [4]. The rest is small-scale work verification and editing of the map in the JOSM editor.

Each stage of work was also preceded by a thorough analysis of official OSM tags [1] – which constitute information about all elements of the natural environment. It was found that the best represented features were those related to relief, land cover and hydrology. In particular, the content regarding land cover (down to a single tree and bush), and the richness of descriptions of relief forms (OSM WIKI, Glossary of landforms [5]) allow the creation of appropriate thematic maps – land cover maps and geomorphological maps.

Strus, P., Górska, A., Brzyski, W., Bobrek, A., & Konderak, N. (2025). Beyond the seventh mountain, beyond the seventh river – OpenStreetMap as a base map in geographical research.

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The principle adopted in JOSM is that we complete the map to the highest degree of accuracy possible using available data and processing capacity. For example, we supplement the terrain coverage for Poland from the available official orthophoto map from the national geoportal with a terrain resolution of 5 cm. The distinction between land cover types is made by students of higher years of geography, so there should not be too many interpretation errors.

Figure 1. UKEN GIS Lab Team and students while listening to the advanced OSM lecture.

What information is completed on the map? As for the relief of the land - valleys and valley types, rock walls, erosion undercuts, landslides and landslide niches.

An additional module of our work is urban micromapping. We check how accurately we can supplement field data so that they can serve two purposes – for students and spatial planning specialists in the analysis and inventory of urban space, and for people with disabilities as a base for accessibility maps used in applications, e.g. blind. For this purpose, we carried out tests of terrain mapping using a geodetic GPS receiver (STONEX 900A). We chose the area on the campus of our university due to the presence of the remains of an old waterbed supplying water to mills and a city moat – a lot of unevenness, steps, suddenly ending sidewalks, etc.

Additionally, we have also started work on old housing estates in Krakow's Nowa Huta district – inhabited mainly by older people, and therefore often beneficiaries of all programs regarding the availability of public facilities and apartments.

Approximately one thousand points were measured in the above locations with an accuracy ranging from 2 mm to 1 cm. In further stages, they will serve as the basis for the point cloud made during unmanned aerial vehicle raids.

A number of additional works were also carried out as part of the project, e.g. wild waste dumps in the Ojców National Park were mapped and marked (we will most likely use the tag *amenity=waste_dump_site*).

All work on the project resulted not only in a significant improvement in the quality of the OSM map, but also in the training of a large team who, in their free time, complete OSM data in their area [6].

Both the map analytical and field stages of the work are still in progress. This is our beginning in the work of OSM, but we would like to use our previous experience in completing OSM data in various places around the world in many task programs, e.g. for UN Mappers and the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT).

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What happens when VGI is threatened? An analysis of the events behind the introduction of rate limiting in OpenStreetMap

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OpenStreetMap (OSM) operates on optimistic principles: it assumes that a diverse crowd can collaboratively agree on project goals and the methods to achieve them. This presumption of goodwill among participants is, for the most part, validated by OSM's success. However, there are instances where these assumptions are challenged, such as disagreements over tag usage [1], the mapping of general feature types [2], or specific entities [3]. When unresolved, these disputes can escalate into "editing wars," where users engage in repeated edits to enforce their views [4]. Despite such conflicts, the involved parties generally do not contest OSM's overarching objective of producing an accurate global map. Deviations from this goal, classified as platform abuse [5], include actions like spamming (e.g., using OSM for promotional purposes) and vandalism, where edits intentionally misrepresent on-the-ground reality. These abuses, particularly vandalism, pose significant risks to the project's success, as an inaccurate map can render OSM unusable in many contexts. Such incidents are not uncommon, as evidenced by an analysis of user bans [6]. Academic studies on this issue have primarily focused on detecting vandalism, e.g. [7], and analyzing specific cases' impacts on data integrity, e.g. [8]. OSM's primary responses to vandalism include post-hoc data reverts, which any user can perform, and user bans issued by the Data Working Group (DWG), the OSM Foundation body responsible for handling data-related issues such as copyright infringement and abuse [9]. Recently, OSM introduced a daily rate limit in response to a particularly severe vandalism case, marking a shift towards proactive vulnerability mitigation [10]. This paper documents and analyzes the events that led to the implementation of the rate limit, aiming to understand better through these events the factors influencing OSM's resilience and vulnerability.

The chain of events began on October 20, 2023, when members of the OSM_Israel Telegram group [11] reported an instance of vandalism. By the following evening, it became apparent that this was part of a coordinated effort involving newly created accounts

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systematically deleting and distorting data, e.g. [12,13]. Despite DWG’s prompt response with bans, new accounts continued to emerge. The timing of these edits, coinciding with Israeli military’s airstrikes on Gaza in response to Hamas’s October 7 attack, along with changeset comments such as “There is no country Israel & Free Palestine,” clearly indicated a political motivation behind the vandalism. Eventually, 13 new accounts (identified here based on bans and changeset comments) responsible for 279 changesets had succeeded in deleting large portions of Tel Aviv (see Fig. 1a), distorting entities across Israel (see Fig. 1b), and even altering coastlines in Lebanon, Turkey, Cyprus, Greece, Egypt, and the Gaza Strip itself, likely due to the automated edits not excluding entities extending beyond Israel, such as the Levantine Sea [14] (see Fig. 1c). One unique case of counter-vandalism was registered when part of the Gaza strip was annexed into Israel “[i]n response to the deletion of Tel Aviv” [15].

Figure 1. Screenshots of the OSM website, 25 October 2024. (a) Data deletion in Tel Aviv’s center; (b) Northern Tel Aviv - diagonal streets are the result of distortions, the orange line is Israel’s border which was also distorted; (c) Beirut, Lebanon, near the US embassy - the coastline (in orange) crosses to land at one point, the international border is also distorted. Source: ©OpenStreetMap contributors.

A secondary chain of events unfolded in response to these attacks, characterized by collaboration between the Israeli mapping community and the DWG. Despite historical tensions between the Israeli community and the DWG [3], a close partnership emerged. On October 22, 2024, a DWG member initiated a dedicated thread on the Israel OSM Community Forum [16] and was subsequently invited to join the OSM_Israel Telegram group, establishing two direct communication channels for reporting new vandal accounts and coordinating data reverts. A clear division of labor emerged: users reported issues, the DWG issued bans and implemented reverts (one highly active Israeli user was unique in also engaging with the reverting processes). The collaboration however extended beyond immediate damage control. Responding to local mappers’ comments in both channels, the DWG member referenced a GitHub issue regarding the possibility of limiting edit volumes [17], explicitly encouraging community members to contribute their thoughts. Although the idea of a rate limiting was not new – the issue had been open since August 2019 – it gained traction after two Israeli community members joined the discussion on October 23, 2023, posting comments which directly addressed the situation in Israel, with one referencing the

comment from the Israel OSM Community Forum in which the DWG member mentioned the issue. This sparked widespread discussion, leading to a new pull request issued by an OSM system administrator on October 29, which he merged into the master branch on November 15, 2023 [18]. Today, the daily rate limit is enforced and has been expanded to include a geographical limit on changeset size [19].

The dynamics behind this significant shift in OSM's strategy – from reactive damage control to proactive vulnerability reduction – offer valuable insights into the governance systems and power dynamics that shape the project's vulnerability and resilience. In the context of data contributions, OSM operates as a 'do-ocracy,' where power is derived from action [20]. Typically, this system is beneficial, as those who contribute more hold greater influence. However, it also introduces a significant vulnerability: the case here shows that within this governance system, any individual user has the power to undermine OSM. The rate limit, designed to reduce this vulnerability by curbing individual power, challenges the do-ocratic model (concerns regarding its impact on active users were indeed voiced in [17] and [18]). Furthermore, the measure's implementation relied on a mechanism foreign to do-ocracy, i.e. mobilizing contributors to support the initiative. This process was necessary because, in terms of management, crowdsourced geodata projects like OSM are governed by a different system comprising three interacting components [21]: the project, where goals and procedures are established, the data-contributing users, and the technical infrastructure. In this model, power is primarily based on position and concentrated within the project sphere, particularly in roles like the OSM system administrator. However, transitions between these spheres are possible, as demonstrated by the ad-hoc coalition formed between the DWG member and community members. Despite the general division of labor, local mappers' involvement in vandalism detection and data reverts blurred the boundaries between the spheres. This interaction supported the DWG member's invitation to local mappers to engage more actively by endorsing the rate limit concept. The two governance systems thus intersected, with a do-ocratic approach used to penetrate the hierarchical structure and effect significant change. However, the outcome further differentiates contributors from the project, shifting more power towards the project and away from individual contributors, thus widening the gap between these two spheres. Indeed, concerns have already been raised regarding the rate limit's impacts [22].

In conclusion, the interplay between these two governance systems in OSM is dynamic, converging when actions facilitate boundary crossings and diverging when the project asserts power over contributors. This tension between reducing vulnerability and enhancing openness is central to the project's evolution: hierarchy reduces vulnerability through greater control, which also creates participation barriers, while a do-ocratic approach fosters both openness and vulnerability. Yet, this interplay is also a source of resilience; the flexibility of boundaries inherent in do-ocracy can expedite adaptation processes, as seen in the temporary coalition's mobilization. However, such efforts must be approached cautiously, as shifts in the balance between the two systems can have profound implications, such as using a do-ocratic approach to limit openness. Additionally, it is noteworthy that other significant vandalism cases, such as those related to the Russia-Ukraine conflict [4], did not lead to substantial changes within OSM. Whether this was due to an inability to mobilize local contributors or other factors remains unclear. Therefore, further research is needed to determine whether the factors outlined here are essential for mitigating vulnerability or represent just one pathway to such outcomes.

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Investigating Corporate Editors in OpenStreetMap

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In recent years, OpenStreetMap (OSM) has evolved from a Volunteered Geographic Information Project to one of the most successful Geospatial Crowdsourcing Platforms. Volunteers, governments, and corporations all make contributions to its global map. Corporate editors (CEs) are the latest entrant in the OSM ecosystem, and their prolific contributions have drawn significant interest from the OSM community as well as the scientific community. In 2018, the OpenStreetMap Foundation introduced a set of Organised Editing Guidelines to address large scale editing such as the ones made by CEs [1]. Despite the guidelines, there is a perceived lack of dialogue and transparency between corporations and the larger community. Previous research has focused on the changing landscape of OSM users with the growth of CEs, cataloguing the global footprint of corporate editing and the map features edited by CEs [2]. Others have studied the impacts of having a dedicated workforce capable of making significant changes to specific map features in a short period of time [3-5]. This study focuses on the CEs themselves. While other research has explored the impacts of CEs' existence, they have not explored who these editors are, and the reasons and conditions for their employment. We sought to learn about the demographic makeup, careers, motivations and community relationships of these individuals. With these objectives, we created an anonymous, 28 question mixed methods survey that was distributed directly to every listed CE account provided in accordance with the Organized Editing Guidelines on the OSMwiki. The results of this survey indicate that there is a correlation between CE job satisfaction and their involvement in the OSM community, and that there is variety in the demographics of the CE population, in the tasks they complete, in the way they interact with the community, and the way they perceive OSM itself.

The response rate to the survey was low as many employers prevented their employees from taking the survey. Thus non-exclusive groups were created based on the responses, previous literature, and our research objectives. Group 1 was composed of corporate editors who were paid an hourly wage (n=20), dubbed the "hourly CEs". Group 2 were editors who are paid an annual salary (n=2). In a similar vein to the hourly CEs, these editors were named the "annual CEs". The juxtaposition of the hourly and annual CEs allowed us to determine what factors contribute to greater job stability, if there is a difference in the way these two groups edit in OSM, their motivations for working in OSM,

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and their interactions with the community. Group 3 was made up of corporate editors who mapped in OSM prior to their employment (n=16). They are labelled the “veterans” due to their experience with OSM. This allows exploring whether prior experiences with OSM are considered an asset and provides additional information on OSM editing as a career since it can be determined if veterans are frequently responsible for the more involved and responsibility-based tasks, such as validation of the edits. Group 4 was composed of editors who edited the same region of the map as their residence (n=10). This group was designated the “locals” as they provide an insight into the value corporations associate with local knowledge and expertise of their corporate editors. These groups were then compared to each other using ANOVA and compared to the population using t-tests in R.

A non-exclusive typology was also created to allow for further analysis of results. This typology was based on the statistical distribution of answers to several matrix questions in the survey (for a full list of survey questions, please see the link in the appendix). The questions were related to the editing behaviours, interactions with community members and community events, and job satisfaction of the CEs. A cumulative score was calculated for each matrix, and any respondents who fell one standard deviation above or below the mean was sorted into the relevant type. The following types of CE were created: heavy (high frequency, high variety edits at work, n=6), light (low frequency, high variety edits at work, n=6), technical (high frequency, high variety mapping technique users, n=6), sporadic (low frequency, high variety mapping technique users n=6), social (high variety, high participation in community related activities, n=5), less social (high variety, low participation in community related activities, n=4), happy (high variety, high satisfaction, n=6), and dissatisfied (high variety, low satisfaction, n=4). These types, paired with the groups created based on literature, allowed for a multi-pronged analysis.

The t-tests indicated that hourly CEs communicated with other OSM users through chat channels like telegram much less frequently (p=0.044). While this is the only method of communication with the community that was significantly different, it should be noted that three of the four remaining communication methods all had p values below 0.15, implying that communication with the community is not done with much frequency across this group. The statistical tests also revealed that annual CEs edit on their own time (p= 0.006), edited the map prior to working as editor (p=0.045), and edit and create roads (p=0.046) and amenities (p=0.029) at a significantly greater rate than the population mean. Annual CEs assigned significantly less importance to learning about OSM and geospatial data (p=0.031) and building technical skills (p=0.025, n=2). Annual CEs participated in global state of the map conferences with much more frequency (p=0.029). They were well below average in their belief that they were learning valuable skills (p= 3.916e-09, n=2) and did not plan to build a career in editing OSM (p=4.994e-09). Annual CEs had a greater number of differences compared to the other groups, but their size (n=2) relative to the population (n=44) is much smaller than any other group. It is also not surprising that this group participated in global state of the map conferences as their familiarity with the community would make them more aware and perhaps more enticed to attend such an event. The only difference between the veterans (n=16) and the population was that they were significantly more likely to participate in regional state of the map conferences (p=0.041). The veterans’ increased likelihood to participate in regional state of the map conferences makes sense as they have increased familiarity with OSM and its community.

The locals made considerably less edits to natural features at work (p=0.004). There

was a strong sentiment of wanting to continue working on projects involving OSM, exceeding the population mean ($p=0.037$). The lower frequency of editing natural features by the locals may have been due to sufficient data already existing within OSM in these regions, or a lack of prioritisation of these features from the corporations who employed these editors. Wishing to continue working in OSM could be explained by the fact that 60% of this group considered improving local data to be very important.

Through ANOVA, we learned that hourly CEs differ from annual CEs ($p=0.0174$), veterans ($p=0.0114$), and locals ($p=0.0274$) for editing amenities when at home. This group also differed from annual CEs ($p=0.0185$), veterans ($p=0.0086$), and locals ($p=0.0351$) for editing building footprints at home. The trend continued across all 12 measures for at home mapping activity. All editors belonging to the annual CEs and the veterans mapped in OSM on their own time, and 90% of locals did so as well. In comparison, only 30% of hourly CEs mapped in OSM on their own time, which would account for why there was a significant difference between this group and at least one other for every question involving at home editing. Hourly CEs differed significantly from locals for editing administrative boundaries ($p=0.0347$) at work. This was likely due to the fact that locals edit on smaller regions – the main characteristic of this group was editing where they work – which limited the range of their editing activities, while over 68% of hourly CEs did so on a global scale.

A profile of a typical CE was created using the mode of each question's response which revealed a general framework of their work week, with 8-hour days (19.5% of respondents), one project meeting per week (62.5% of respondents), and good relationships between colleagues (51.6% of respondents). This profile also revealed that the typical CE lived in North America (63.6% of respondents), worked full-time (88.9% of respondents) with their employer of at least 12 months (21.4% of respondents), at their first paid OSM editing job (81.0% of respondents) where they are paid an hourly wage (60.6% of respondents). On a daily basis they edited all over the world (50.0% of respondents), used JOSM for most of their editing (68.4% of respondents), traced satellite imagery (50.0% of respondents), corrected the shape of geometric objects (51.4% of respondents), validated existing features (42.8% of respondents), and corrected the attributes associated with features (42.8% of respondents). If they require assistance, they consult with coworkers through internal channels (91.4% of respondents), consult the OSMwiki (88.6% of respondents), or discuss the challenge with coworkers (85.7% of respondents). Most did not map in OSM before their employment (56.8% of respondents), but started contributing to the map once a week (62.5% of respondents) on their own time. They often participated in mapping parties (32.2% of respondents), but otherwise rarely participated in other community events. They would like to continue to work in projects involving OSM (58.1% of respondents), enjoyed working with the coworkers (51.6% of respondents), wanted to continue a career in mapping (48.4% of respondents), and feel that they learned valuable skills at their jobs (45.2% of respondents).

Comparing the heavy and light type CEs revealed some of the nuances of corporate editing. Though these two types represent the greatest and least amount of editing, light CEs have greater job security, with 75% paid monthly compared to 83% of heavy editors being paid hourly. This may also be due to light editors' increased exposure to OSM, as these editors both mapped before they were hired to do so (60% of type) and mapped on their own time (80% of type). These differences likely suggest that there are a variety of roles for CEs, some of which do not entail editing itself. The idea of different roles is also supported

through the comparison of technical and sporadic users, as both used a variety of techniques, but again we saw a disparity of editing times (1-8 hours a day for technical CEs compared to 0-1 for sporadic CEs). Sporadic CEs were limited in the frequency and variety of mapping techniques used because they had limited opportunities to use them. Contrary to the heavy and light editors however, both the technical and sporadic types were paid mostly hourly, with rates of 50 and 60%, respectively. There was significant overlap between community involvement and job satisfaction within CEs. 80% of social CEs are also happy CEs, and less social editors make up 50% of the dissatisfied type. Less social and dissatisfied editors are fairly homogeneous, all working full time, paid hourly, not mapping in OSM before they were hired, nor mapping on their own time, and living in North America. In comparison, social and happy CEs had an even split of employment styles, with a mix of full time, part time, and freelance workers, who lived in four different regions around the world. They all mapped in OSM before their hiring, continued to map on their own time, and they find their work to be exciting or engaging. While it is unsurprising that having interest in your work leads to greater satisfaction, the results of this survey showed there is undoubtedly a connection between satisfaction and mapping in OSM outside the workplace, as well as in engagement with the community.

Unfortunately, we encountered several challenges in reaching out to individual editors as the organisations they work for explicitly prevented them from answering the survey. This had a significant impact on our ability to collect responses, as over half the CE community was made unavailable to this study. Over the course of this research, we reached out to 34 corporations and 1985 CEs, receiving 39 complete responses and an additional 5 usable partial responses. This represents a response rate of 2.2% meaning that we must establish that our results do not serve as a definite representation of CEs. Low participation was also the rationale for the multi-pronged analysis, as we sought to learn as much as possible from a limited population. Though all CEs reserve the right to not participate in this study, the blanket refusal seen by some corporations is at odds with the autonomous agency which has been a tradition of OSM. At one company, all direct messages sent to any of their CE accounts on OSM redirect to the inbox of their manager, which raises similar questions. While our results may not provide a faithful representation of all CEs, our work furthers conversation regarding these workers and broaches the topic of their agency.

Survey questions, statistical analysis, figures, and a list of contacted corporations are available at: <https://github.com/Hoferek/Investigating-Corporate-Editors-OSMScience-2024>.

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Assessing the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of road data in OpenStreetMap

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OpenStreetMap (OSM) relies on crowdsourced contributions and lacks strict quality control, ensuring data quality has thus become a key area of research [1]. Understanding and addressing these data quality issues can facilitate unlocking OSM's full potential for diverse applications. OSM data quality assessment methods can be divided into two broad categories: extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic quality assessment methods compare OSM data with a reference dataset (e.g., authoritative data sources). This is where most initial research on OSM data quality started from [2-4]. Yet, a reference dataset may not always be available. On this ground, researchers called for attention to intrinsic indicators of OSM data quality [5] and proposed intrinsic data quality measures based on a snapshot of data, data history, and metadata [5-9].

It is crucial to acknowledge that the quality of OSM data is not a one-size-fits-all metric. Rather, it heavily depends on the purpose of the application domain, known as "fitness-for-use" [5,10]. The diverse application potentials introduce dynamic data requirements. Navigation is one of the primary application domains in which OSM plays a pivotal role. Among them, vehicular traffic constitutes a significant portion of road usage and has a substantial impact on urban mobility and infrastructure planning. Additionally, the complexities involved in automotive navigation and traffic systems require a higher level of data accuracy and reliability, making it a compelling starting point for investigating intrinsic road data quality.

In the context of car driving, the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of road data are particularly important [11]. Attribute accuracy refers to the correctness and logical coherence of attributes associated with road features, such as speed limits, road classifications, and turn restrictions [12]. Logical consistency ensures that the road network data follows the correct topological rules, such as proper connectivity of different road classes. The attribute accuracy and logical consistency of OSM road data are essential for traffic planning and supporting navigation applications.

To address the challenges of evaluating OSM data quality for navigation, when a reference dataset is unavailable, this research narrows its focus to the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of OSM road data. Our current work in progress uses the Munich city centre as a case study.

To assess attribute accuracy, we first identify important attributes related to car driving, such as speed limits, number of lanes, and one-way information [13-15]. Then, our method assesses the attribute completeness of each segment as the weighted sum of the value of each attribute divided by the weighted sum of each attribute with its maximum value. The attribute completeness provides us with a first overview of the attribute data. For instance, as of June 30, 2024, the completeness level of the Munich city centre is 67.185%.

In the next step, a set of rules based on country-specific traffic laws is defined, and the relevant attributes are checked against these rules. So far, we have looked into the traffic law in Germany [16] and the aggregated default speed limits on the OSM wiki [17]. We defined rules accordingly for speed limits regarding the “highway” type. To determine whether a road was in an urban or rural area, relevant attributes like “zone:maxspeed”, “source:maxspeed”, “maxspeed:type”, “zone:traffic” were checked. Then the algorithm verified the value of road segments against the rules. When a mismatch occurred, these road segments were identified and considered as inaccurate. The inaccuracy of the speed limit is calculated as the length of road segments with an inaccurate “maxspeed” value divided by the total road length with the “maxspeed” attribute. Our case study in the Munich city centre revealed a low attribute inaccuracy rate of 0.078%. However, some discrepancies were detected, such as residential roads with a speed limit of 60 km/h (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. An example of a detected road segment with inaccurate maxspeed value. It is marked as a residential road while having a maxspeed of 60 km/h.

Regarding logical consistency, a set of rules was defined based on country-specific conventions, and inconsistent cases were detected against these rules. We acknowledge that different regions in the world have different road construction and mapping conventions. So far, we have conducted our case study in Germany, and defined rules for the values of the “highway” tag. These rules include: the connection of different classes of roads should be logically consistent (i.e., a way with a high level of importance in the road network should not be connected directly to a way with a much lower level of importance);

motorways can only be connected to “motorway” or “motorway_link”; a link road should be connected to its corresponding highway. For each inconsistency type, we calculated the inconsistency rate as the length of affected roads divided by the total length. Since we considered the aforementioned inconsistency the same weight, the logical inconsistency was then calculated as the sum. As such, we are flexible in adding new rules to the indicator. For example, regarding the aforementioned type of logical inconsistency, the Munich city centre has rates of 0.916%, 0.106%, and 0.004%, respectively. The overall logical inconsistency rate is 1.026%.

Our work aims to assess OSM road data quality with a focus on car driving. Current work-in-progress proposed indicators to assess attribute accuracy, with a focus on speed limits and methods for estimating the logical consistency of road data. Checking the speed limits and their sources against default speed limits offers an initial assessment to attribute inaccuracy, as the speed limit is one of the most important road attributes related to car driving. It also provides the starting point of a scalable approach to extend to a global scale. Worth noting for attribute inaccuracy is that this indicator assesses the data against the country's default speed limits. In reality, many roads are regulated by traffic signs, with more strict speed limits. If a road segment is not flagged as inaccurate, it does not necessarily mean it is accurate. This indicator shows the road attribute quality, but should not be understood as indicating accuracy. In addition, exceptional cases may exist, for different temporal scales, which should also be treated cautiously.

As an indicator aggregated by individual measures, logical consistency offers varying levels of detail, thus suitable for different levels of decision-making. The logical inconsistency rate presents a high-level overview of the data quality. Users can make informed decisions on whether to use OSM as a data source for specified areas. Once the high-level decision is made, examining the error types and searching for relevant solutions to process data can be the next step. When the inconsistency rate is low and occurs at the individual case level, reviewing the detected cases is more beneficial than focusing on the calculated inconsistency rate.

In the next step, we plan to conduct a user study with navigation service providers, aiming at identifying crucial attributes for routing services tailored to car driving, in order to improve the attribute completeness indicator. In terms of attribute inaccuracy, we plan to scale it up to the global level, by implementing the default speed limits aggregated from contributors on the OSM Wiki [17], as well as using large language models to help verify the aggregated speed limits. As exception cases for speed limits exist in reality, we can consider introducing other tags into the analysis. Another possibility would be leveraging the crowd wisdom further to collect exceptional cases, by potentially collecting such data in the OSM wiki page.

With the proposed assessment, OSM data users can verify road data quality in terms of attribute accuracy and logical consistency, before their intended use. With the evaluation method, we also aim to inform the potential improvement of OSM road data quality, especially for navigation.

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